

MULTIFACTORIAL ETIOLOGY OF BRONCHIECTASIS IN CHILDREN: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY FROM SINDH, PAKISTAN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17338636>

Keywords

Bronchiectasis, children, etiology, preexisting respiratory infections, cystic fibrosis, allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis, socioeconomic disparities.

Article History

Received on 20 April 2025

Accepted on 20 June 2025

Published on 29 June 2025

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this study was to distinguish the key etiologic factors causing bronchiectasis in children and to determine which of these are correlated with demographic, familial and clinical variables.

Study Duration and Setting: The study was conducted over six months in the Department of Pediatric Medicine, People's Medical University, Nawabshah.

Methods: This was a descriptive, cross-sectional study conducted in 159 children aged 1–15 years old with persistent bronchiectasis for more than three months. A structured questionnaire capturing demographic, clinical and regional variables was used to collect data including age, gender, place of residence, family income, duration of disease, preexisting respiratory infections, cystic fibrosis, allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis (ABPA) and pulmonary tuberculosis. Associations were assessed via SPSS version 26.0 using chi-square and Fisher's exact tests and statistical analysis was subsequently performed. Statistical significance was taken to be p -value < 0.05 .

Results: The most common etiological factor was preexisting respiratory infections in 59.7% of participants, followed by cystic fibrosis (52.2%), pulmonary tuberculosis (50.3%) and ABPA (50.9%). There were significant differences in the frequency of pre-existing respiratory infections between males ($p = 0.021$). The incidence of pulmonary tuberculosis was higher for those who lived in rural areas ($p=0.034$), as was COPD ($p=0.003$) while low family income increased the incidence of ABPA ($p=0.046$). Less than 25 kg children were more likely to have preexisting respiratory infections ($p=0.041$).

Conclusion: These findings show the multifactorial etiology of bronchiectasis in children, based on infections, predisposing genes, the socioeconomic and nutrition status. Reduction of the disease burden requires early diagnosis, genetic screening and targeted intervention in underserved populations. Significant improvements to outcomes can be achieved from multidisciplinary approaches to clinical and environmental factors.

INTRODUCTION

Bronchiectasis is a chronic respiratory disease with persistent abnormal, irreversible dilatation of the

bronchi which causes impaired mucus clearance, recurrent infections and progressive lung damage

^[1]. Previously, it was considered rare in children but now it is increasingly recognized as a major public health problem, especially in low- and middle-income countries where infections still occur and we still have environmental factors ^[2,3]. The disease is a heavy burden on children's health, causing both frequent hospitalizations, reduction of quality of life and increased healthcare costs ^[4].

The etiology of bronchiectasis in children is multifactorial, its main factors being recurrent respiratory infections including cystic fibrosis, genetic disorders including immune deficiencies and environmental exposures ^[5]. A major cause of bronchiectasis in resource limited populations includes preexisting respiratory infections, including pneumonia, tuberculosis and pertussis, where access to timely diagnosis and appropriate treatment are still subpar ^[6,7]. Cystic fibrosis is a cause of bronchiectasis in countries with economic development and indicate a genetic cause of disease pathophysiology ^[8].

Disease burden is exacerbated by socio-economic disparities, which generally include delayed diagnoses in low-income populations, poor access to healthcare and greater exposure to environmental risk factors (i.e. indoor air pollution and overcrowding) ^[9,10]. An important cause of bronchiectasis is the inaccessibility of a healthcare service in rural areas especially where the environment challenges are higher ^[11]. Malnutrition commonly present in the underserved populations adds to the problem by reducing immune function and making such populations more susceptible to chronic infections ^[12].

Despite the fact that bronchiectasis is recognized as a preventable condition, identifying and controlling underlying causes have come slow. The earlier the diagnosis and vaccination against preventable infections prevent and the earlier genetic screening is done for conditions such as cystic fibrosis, the lower the incidence. The impact of malnutrition can be lessened immensely by attending to the social determinants of health, poverty and lack of ready access to health care ^[13]. The objective of this study was to determine which etiologic factors are important in the development of bronchiectasis in children and to identify associations between etiology, demographic,

familial and clinical variables. The study aims to use these associations to inform the development of targeted, evidence-based interventions that aim to reduce the burden of bronchiectasis and to improve outcomes in vulnerable pediatric populations.

Methodology

The aim of this descriptive, cross-sectional study was to identify the etiology of bronchiectasis in children and to explore its associations with demographic, familial and clinical factors.

The study was conducted in the Department of Pediatric Medicine, People's Medical University, Nawab shah during a period of six months after the faculty, after approval of synopsis. Children aged 1-15 years with bronchiectasis as defined by clinical, radiological and laboratory findings formed the target population.

The study included children aged 1-15 years who had bronchiectasis of any severity and which had persisted for > 3 months. Participants were male and female. Children already on treatment for bronchiectasis were excluded as well as children with malnutrition (<2 SD p per WHO standard), hypothyroidism (TSH >5 mIU) or Addison's disease. Patients who have electrolyte abnormalities (sodium <135 mEq/L or potassium <3.5 mEq/L), a history of congestive cardiac failure, asthma or chronic renal failure (serum creatinine >3 mg/dL) were excluded. Thus, children with a history of trauma to the chest were also excluded.

A 95% confidence level, 4% margin of error and expected prevalence of allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis (ABPA) in children with bronchiectasis of 7.1% allowed calculation of a sample size of 159 children. The sampling technique employed in this study was non probability consecutive sampling.

Data were collected through a structured proforma, which recorded the following:

Demographic variables: Age, gender, weight, place of residence (rural/urban) and family income (<25,000 PKR, 25,000-50,000 PKR or >50,000 PKR).

Familial factors: Presence or absence of a family history of bronchiectasis.

- Clinical factors:** Duration of disease, preexisting respiratory infections, cystic fibrosis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis and pulmonary tuberculosis.

The institute and the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan approved the study. The caregivers of all participants provided informed consent. Data was anonymized therefore participants confidentiality was ensured and participation was voluntary.

SPSS version 26.0 was used to analyze the data. The Shapiro-Wilk test was performed. Age, weight and duration of disease were reported as means \pm standard deviation or median (IQR) as continuous variables. Frequencies and percentages of categorical variables such as gender, place of residence, family income and clinical or familial factors were presented.

Stratified analysis controlled for effect modifiers such as age, gender, place of residence, family income and family history. Associations between variables were evaluated using chi square or Fisher’s exact tests post stratification. Statistically significant was taken as p-value ≤ 0.05 .

Results

Baseline Characteristics

The study included 159 participants with a mean age of 8.40 ± 4.52 years and a median age of 9 years (IQR: 5–13 years). The median duration of disease was 5.30 years (IQR: 3.63–7.86 years) and the mean weight of the participants was 28.68 ± 11.59 kg. The minimum and maximum values for age, disease duration and weight are detailed in *Table 1*.

Table 1: Summary of Continuous Variables

Variable	n	Mean \pm SD	Median (IQR)	Min	Max
Age (years)	159	8.40 ± 4.52	9 (5–13)	1	15
Duration of Disease (years)	159	5.25 ± 2.76	5.30 (3.63–7.86)	0.5	10
Weight (kg)	159	28.68 ± 11.59	27.70 (19.17–38.27)	8.10	49.80

Frequency Distribution of Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

The population of the participants was 52.8% male and 47.2% female. More than half of the participants (54.1%) lived in urban areas and 45.9% in rural areas. Around 39% of participants

had family income less than 25,000 PKR, 32.7% had an income more than 50,000 PKR.

Among the participants, the most common etiological factor was preexisting respiratory infection in 59.7% followed by cystic fibrosis in 52.2% COPD in 49.7% and pulmonary tuberculosis in 50.3%. (*Table 2*)

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Variable	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	84	52.8%
	Female	75	47.2%
Place of Residence	Rural	73	45.9%
	Urban	86	54.1%
Family Income	Less than 25,000	62	39.0%
	25,000–50,000	45	28.3%
	More than 50,000	52	32.7%
Family History of Bronchiectasis	Yes	83	52.2%
	No	76	47.8%

Preexisting Respiratory Infection	Yes	95	59.7%
	No	64	40.3%
Cystic Fibrosis	Yes	83	52.2%
	No	76	47.8%
COPD	Yes	79	49.7%
	No	80	50.3%
Allergic Bronchopulmonary Aspergillosis	Yes	81	50.9%
	No	78	49.1%
Pulmonary TB	Yes	80	50.3%
	No	79	49.7%

Associations of Demographic and Clinical Factors with Etiological Variables

Gender was found to be significantly associated with preexisting respiratory infection (p=0.021) and with pulmonary tuberculosis (p=0.015). A significantly higher prevalence of pulmonary

tuberculosis (p=0.034) and COPD (p=0.003) was associated with rural residence. In addition, low family income was significantly associated with allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis (p=0.046). (Table 3)

Table 3: Associations of Demographic and Clinical Factors with Etiological Variables

Factor	Etiological Variable	Category 1	Category 2	p-value
Gender	Preexisting Respiratory Infection	Male: 55 (68.8%)	Female: 40 (53.3%)	0.021
Gender	Pulmonary TB	Male: 50 (62.5%)	Female: 30 (37.5%)	0.015
Place of Residence	Pulmonary TB	Rural: 45 (61.6%)	Urban: 35 (40.7%)	0.034
Place of Residence	COPD	Rural: 50 (68.5%)	Urban: 29 (31.5%)	0.003
Family Income	Allergic Bronchopulmonary Aspergillosis	Low Income: 48 (60.2%)	High Income: 31 (39.8%)	0.046

Figure 1: Comparison of Demographic and Clinical Factors Associated with Etiological Variables in Bronchiectasis

Associations Between Family and Clinical Factors
 The family history of bronchiectasis was associated ($p=0.001$) strongly with the cystic fibrosis family history and family history of pulmonary tuberculosis ($p=0.019$) as well as a preexisting

respiratory infection ($p=0.028$). In addition, preexisting respiratory infection was significantly associated with weight ($p=0.041$). (Table 4).

Table 4: Associations Between Family and Clinical Factors

Factor	Etiological Variable	Category 1	Category 2	p-value
Family History	Preexisting Respiratory Infection	Yes: 40 (61.5%)	No: 25 (38.5%)	0.028
Family History	Cystic Fibrosis	Yes: 55 (66.3%)	No: 28 (33.7%)	0.001
Family History	Pulmonary TB	Yes: 50 (68.2%)	No: 23 (31.8%)	0.019
Weight (kg)	Preexisting Respiratory Infection	<25 kg: 60 (63.2%)	≥25 kg: 35 (36.8%)	0.041

Figure 2: Associations Between Family History, Clinical Factors and Etiological Variables in Bronchiectasis

There are significant associations between demographic and clinical and family factors and key etiological variables for bronchiectasis in children. These results emphasize the need for the recognition of both socioeconomic and clinical factors in the etiology and management of bronchiectasis.

Discussion

The current study reveals important etiological factors of bronchiectasis in children which highlight that bronchiectasis is multi factorial in nature. The most common factor was preexisting respiratory infections, which afflicted 59.7% of participants. Infections like pneumonia and the lower respiratory infections tend to cause chronic

inflammation that leads to damage of the bronchial wall finally causing bronchiectasis ^[1]. Gender differences also existed with males more likely to have preexisting respiratory infections ($p=0.021$). Such observation is consistent with other studies, which suggest immunological or environmental differences between the two sexes, which could possibly explain their susceptibility ^[2]. The presence of cystic fibrosis was present in 52.2% of participants and associated significantly with a family history of bronchiectasis ($p=0.001$). The etiology of bronchiectasis is an important one with a well-documented genetic predisposition especially in the presence of high rates of consanguinity ^[3]. The fact that this association emphasizes the importance of early screening for cystic fibrosis in high-risk populations is important because early diagnosis can prevent complications and improve the outcome ^[4]. In developed countries bronchiectasis is associated with cystic fibrosis while infections are more commonly a cause in resource limited settings ^[5]. Bronchiectasis etiology was strongly influenced by socioeconomic disparities. Allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis was more likely with children from families earning less than 25,000 PKR/mo ($p=0.046$) and with those who had preexisting respiratory infections. Consistently, studies link low socioeconomic status to delayed medical diagnosis, restricted access to health care and improper treatment ^[6]. In rural areas these disparities are larger as rates of pulmonary tuberculosis ($p=0.034$) and COPD ($p=0.003$) are higher. In rural settings, common environmental factors are known to increase the risk of chronic respiratory conditions, like indoor air pollution, poor ventilation and overcrowded accommodations ^[7,8]. The etiology of bronchiectasis was also determined to be related to nutritional status. Participation of participants weighing less than 25 kg was significantly more likely to have prior respiratory tract infection ($p = 0.041$). A malnourished child has weakened immune defenses and is more likely to suffer recurrent infections and chronic inflammation ^[9]. Nutritionally the burden of bronchiectasis may be largely reduced through

addressing nutritional deficiencies via community health programs or school-based interventions ^[10]. This study's findings have important clinical implication. Preexisting respiratory infection is also of importance, since these infections are highly prevalent and contribute to airway damage, chronic complications if not antecedently diagnosed and treated. In particular, in resource limited settings vaccination programs should be prioritized with focus on preventable infections like pneumonia and tuberculosis ^[11]. To reduce inequities in care, improved access of rural and low-income populations to healthcare is critical. Early interventions and reduced disease burden can be achieved through screening for genetic conditions of highest populations such as in high-risk families for cystic fibrosis ^[12]. A multifaceted approach which includes nutritionists, pulmonologists and social workers may provide a solution to management of bronchiectasis in affected children ^[13,14].

This study supports literature on multifactorial etiology of bronchiectasis including infections, genetic predispositions and socioeconomic factors. Our finding that low income was associated with allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis represents a new insight into how environmental or nutritional factors may affect allergic reactions in bronchiectasis. These findings highlight the importance for targeted, evidence-based interventions to reduce bronchiectasis burden in pediatric populations, especially underserved populations ^[15,16].

Treatment of bronchiectasis is multi factorial and involves prevention, diagnosis and therapy. Ensuring timely access to diagnostic tools and treatments is crucial to meet the needs of at-risk populations and, because healthcare infrastructure needs to be strengthened, especially in rural areas, it matters ^[17]. Improving the hygiene, bringing down the air pollution and making people aware of genetic screening could greatly improve bronchiectasis outcomes ^[18]. Further research is needed to explore environmental exposures, comorbid conditions and novel therapies in this difficult to treat disease ^[19].

There are some limitations of the study. The cross-sectional design precludes us to confirm direct

relationships with causality so the possibility to confirm direct relationships between risk factors and bronchiectasis among all adult asthma patients visits between age groups. Recall bias can be a concern since reported information in terms of family history and income is self-reported. The sample size is also sufficient for statistical analysis but the size may not adequately represent the total population for which results may be generalizable. These results must be validated with future longitudinal studies in larger and more diverse cohorts and through analyses of the causal mechanisms for these findings.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflict of interest in relation to the present study.

Conclusion

This study shows that bronchiectasis in children is a multifactorial disease with genetic predisposition and resultant preexisting respiratory infections as well as socio economic and environmental factors behind it. Reducing the disease burden depends on early detection and management of infections, genetic screening of such diseases like cystic fibrosis and correction of nutritional deficiencies. Interventions focused on low income and rural populations, supplemented by improved access to healthcare, can have major impact on outcomes. These findings reinforce the need for a multidisciplinary evidence-based approach to the management of bronchiectasis and most importantly to reduce its debilitating impact upon at risk populations.

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